

Volumetric, compressibility and transport behaviour of some α -amino acids in water and aqueous glycerine at 303.15 K

R. Palani* and Y. Reeginal

Department of Physics, D.D.E., Annamalai University, Annamalainagar-608 002, Tamilnadu, India

E-mail : palani_physics06@yahoo.co.in

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Abstract : Density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) have been measured for L-glutamine, L-asparagine and L-lysine in water and aqueous glycerine (0, 0.5 and 1 mol dm⁻³) at 303.15 K. These measurements have been performed to evaluate some important parameters viz. adiabatic compressibility (β), molar hydration number (n_H), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molar volume (ϕ_V), limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_V^0) and their constants (S_K , S_V), transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$) and viscosity A and B coefficients of Jones-Dole equation. The results have been discussed in terms of solute-co-solute and ion-solvent interaction.

Keywords : Ultrasonic velocity, apparent molar compressibility, apparent molar volume, hydration number, transfer volume.

Introduction

Salt solutions are known to influence the stability and structure of proteins. Salt induced electrostatic forces are known to play vital role in modifying the protein structure by affecting properties like solubility, denaturation and activity of enzymes¹. Amino acids are the fundamental structural units of proteins. In recent years, there have been numerous experimental investigations on proteins. Thermodynamic studies of amino acid systems are useful to understand several biochemical processes such as protein hydration, denaturation, aggregation etc.². The properties and behaviour of amino acids in solutions have always been a matter of interest mainly because amino acids are, among other compounds, the basic structural building units of biomolecules³. L-Amino acids are used in many biological processes in human body like transamination, decarboxylation and metabolism. On the other hand, L-amino acids are also involved in intercellular metabolism and operate specific transport systems of the plasma membrane. Polyhydroxy alcohols are known for stabilizing the native conformation of globular proteins⁴⁻⁶. Glycerol is an important polyhydroxy compound which finds application in the pharmaceutical and cosmetic industry. Glycerol (C₃H₈O₃) is a strongly hygroscopic and viscous liquid. It has three hydrophilic alcoholic hydroxyl

(-OH) groups that are responsible for its solubility in water. It is an important component of fats and oils. It is widely used in personal care products, drugs, foods and beverages. Water remains one of the important components of glycerol. Hence the study of the physical properties of amino acids in aqueous glycerine mixture is of considerable importance.

Therefore, in order to understand the behaviour of proteins in aqueous glycerine solutions, we have studied the volumetric, transport and compressibilities for some α -amino acids in aqueous glycerine solutions at 303.15 K. In this study, we report the values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of L-glutamine, L-asparagine and L-lysine in water and aqueous glycerine (0.5 and 1.0 mol dm⁻³) at 303.15 K. Various parameters like adiabatic compressibility (β), molar hydration number (n_H), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molar volume (ϕ_V), limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_V^0) and their constants (S_K , S_V), transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_V^0$) and viscosity A and B coefficients of Jones-Dole equation⁷ respectively were calculated from density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity data. All these parameters are discussed in terms of ion-solvent and solute-co-solute interactions occurring between amino acids and aqueous glycerine solution.

Materials and method :

Analytical reagent grade (AR) and spectroscopic reagent grade (SR) with minimum assay of 99.9% of L-glutamine, L-asparagine and L-lysine and glycerine were obtained from E. Merck, Germany and Sd Fine chemicals, India, which are used as such without further purification. Water used in the experiments were deionised, distilled and degassed prior to making solutions. Aqueous solutions of glycerine (0.5 and 1.0 mol dm⁻³) were prepared by volume and used on the day they were prepared. Solution of amino acids of 0.02–0.1 mol dm⁻³ were made by volume on the molarity concentration scale with a precision of $\pm 1 \times 10^{-4}$ giving an electronic digital balance (Model : Shimadzu AX-200). The density was determined using a specific gravity bottle by relative measurement method with an accuracy of ± 0.01 kg m⁻³. An Ostwald's viscometer (10 ml) was used for the viscosity measurement. Efflux time was determined using a digital chronometer to within ± 0.01 s. An ultrasonic interferometer having the frequency of 3 MHz (Mittal Enterprises, New Delhi, Model : F-81) with an overall accuracy of $\pm 0.1\%$ has been used for velocity measurement. An electronically digital operated constant temperature bath (RAAGA Industries) has been used to circulate water through the double walled measuring cell made up of steel containing the experimental solution at the desired temperature. The accuracy in the temperature measurement is ± 0.1 K.

Theory and calculations :

Using the measured data, the following volumetric, compressibility and transport parameters have been calculated using the standard relations.

Adiabatic compressibility,

$$\beta = \frac{1}{U^2 \rho} \quad (1)$$

Molar hydration number has been computed using the relation,

$$n_H = \left(\frac{n_1}{n_2} \right) \left(1 - \frac{\beta}{\beta_0} \right) \quad (2)$$

where β and β_0 are adiabatic compressibilities of solution and solvent respectively, n_1 and n_2 are number of moles of solvent and solute, respectively.

The apparent molar compressibility has been calculated from relation,

$$\varphi_K = \frac{1000}{m\rho_0} (\rho_0\beta - \rho\beta_0) + \left(\frac{\beta_0 M}{\rho_0} \right) \quad (3)$$

where β , ρ and β_0 , ρ_0 are the adiabatic compressibility and density of solution and solvent respectively, m is the molar concentration of the solute and M the molecular mass of the solute. φ_K is the function of m as obtained by Gucker⁸ from Debye-Huckel theory⁹ and is given by,

$$\varphi_K = \varphi_K^0 + S_K m^{1/2} \quad (4)$$

where φ_K^0 is the limiting apparent molar compressibility at infinite dilution and S_K is a constant. φ_K^0 and S_K of eq. (4) have been evaluated by the least square method.

The apparent molar volume φ_v has been calculated using the relation,

$$\varphi_v = \left(\frac{M}{\rho} \right) - \frac{1000(\rho - \rho_0)}{m\rho\rho_0} \quad (5)$$

The apparent molar volume φ_v has been found to differ with concentration according to Masson¹⁰ empirical relation as,

$$\varphi_v = \varphi_v^0 + S_v m^{1/2} \quad (6)$$

where φ_v^0 is the limiting apparent molar volume at infinite dilution and S_v is a constant and these values were determined by least square method.

Transfer volume ($\Delta\varphi_v^0$) of each amino acid from water to aqueous glycerine solutions have been calculated by the equation,

$$\Delta\varphi_v^0 = \varphi_v^0 \text{ (in aqueous glycerine solution)} - \varphi_v^0 \text{ (in water)} \quad (7)$$

The viscosity (A and B) coefficients for the amino acids in aqueous glycerine solutions were calculated from the Jones-Dole equation^{7,11},

$$\frac{\eta}{\eta_0} = 1 + Am^{1/2} + Bm \quad (8)$$

where, η and η_0 are the viscosities of the solution and solvent respectively and m is the molar concentration of the solute. A is determined by the ionic attraction theory of Falkenhagen-Vernon and therefore also called Falkenhagen coefficient¹¹, B or Jones-Dole coefficient is an empirical constant determined by ion-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The experimental values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) for different molar composition of each of the three amino acids viz. L-glutamine, L-asparagine and L-lysine in water + glycerine mixtures (0, 0.5 and 1.0 mol dm⁻³) at 303.15 K are shown in Table 1. Further, the values of adiabatic compressibility (β),

suggests a moderate strong electrolytic nature in which the solutes (amino acids) tend to attract the solvent (aqueous glycerine) molecules. Molecular association is thus responsible for the observed increase in density and ultrasonic velocity in these mixtures. The increase of ultrasonic velocity in these solutions may be attributed to the cohesion brought about by the ionic hydration. It is known

Table 1. Values of density (ρ), viscosity (η) and ultrasonic velocity (U) of amino acids in aqueous glycerine solutions at 303.15 K

Molarity (M) (mol dm ⁻³)	ρ (kg m ⁻³)			η ($\times 10^{-3}$ Nsm ⁻²)			U (m s ⁻¹)		
	Water + glycerine			Water + glycerine			Water + glycerine		
	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M
System-I : Water + glycerine + L-glutamine									
0.00	995.0	1008.1	1018.9	0.7973	0.9269	1.0780	1510.0	1521.3	1532.2
0.02	996.9	1009.2	1020.0	0.8157	0.9288	1.0815	1510.3	1533.4	1539.2
0.04	998.1	1010.7	1021.5	0.8364	0.9365	1.1138	1513.0	1540.2	1542.0
0.06	999.3	1011.9	1022.8	0.8825	0.9477	1.1330	1515.8	1548.6	1552.9
0.08	1000.9	1013.0	1024.7	0.9695	0.9494	1.1602	1526.0	1552.0	1561.4
0.10	1002.2	1014.4	1026.3	0.9747	0.9576	1.1904	1548.4	1556.2	1577.1
System-II : Water + glycerine + L-asparagine									
0.00	995.0	1008.1	1018.9	0.7973	0.9269	1.0780	1510.0	1521.3	1532.2
0.02	997.7	1009.8	1020.9	0.8110	0.9318	1.0845	1514.5	1534.7	1556.0
0.04	999.2	1011.2	1022.7	0.8236	0.9439	1.1788	1517.4	1542.5	1562.8
0.06	1002.1	1012.4	1023.9	0.8324	0.9504	1.1960	1540.0	1552.4	1565.5
0.08	1003.9	1013.9	1025.3	0.8415	0.9541	1.3806	1553.0	1556.4	1568.4
0.10	1005.4	1015.1	1027.1	0.8505	0.9598	1.4565	1560.3	1562.6	1579.0
System-III : Water + glycerine + L-lysine									
0.00	995.0	1008.1	1018.9	0.7973	0.9269	1.0780	1510.0	1521.3	1532.2
0.02	998.3	1011.9	1022.2	0.8304	0.9434	1.1338	1512.4	1523.0	1538.3
0.04	999.8	1013.3	1024.5	0.8435	0.9825	1.1950	1519.0	1527.2	1547.9
0.06	1002.3	1014.1	1026.4	1.0075	0.9870	1.2233	1524.9	1534.6	1549.2
0.08	1004.4	1016.0	1027.9	1.1039	1.0036	1.4731	1533.0	1535.2	1554.0
0.10	1006.8	1018.9	1029.2	1.1876	1.0530	1.5771	1544.4	1558.2	1574.0

molar hydration number (n_H), apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K), apparent molar volume (ϕ_v), limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K^0) and limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_v^0) and their constants (S_K , S_v), transfer volume ($\Delta\phi_v^0$) and viscosity A and B coefficients of Jones-Dole equation are given in Tables 2-4.

In all the three amino acids system (Table 1), the values of density (ρ) and ultrasonic velocity (U) increases with the increase in molar concentration of amino acids as well as glycerine content. This increasing trend sug-

gests a moderate strong electrolytic nature in which the solutes (amino acids) tend to attract the solvent (aqueous glycerine) molecules. Molecular association is thus responsible for the observed increase in density and ultrasonic velocity in these mixtures. The increase of ultrasonic velocity in these solutions may be attributed to the cohesion brought about by the ionic hydration. It is known that water + glycerine mixtures of L-glutamine, L-asparagine and L-lysine contain in addition to the uncharged molecules NH_2CH_2COOH , an electrically neutral molecule viz. $NH_3^+CH_2COO^-$ dipolarions (Zwitterions). When the amino acids are dissolved in water + glycerine mixtures, the cations NH_3^+ and the anions COO^- are formed. The water molecules are attached to the ions strongly by the electrostatic forces, which introduce a greater cohesion in the solutions. Thus the cohesion increases with the increase of amino acid concentration in the solutions.

The increased association observed in these solutions, may also be due to water structure enhancement brought about by the increase in electrostriction in the presence of glycerine. The electrostriction effect which brings about the shrinkage in the volume of solvent, caused by the Zwitterionic portion of the amino acids is increased in mixed solvents as compared to that in pure water. This effect is similar to the result of Ragouramane *et al.*¹².

From Table 2, it is observed that the values of adiabatic compressibility decreases with increase in concentration of amino acids as well as glycerine in the mixtures. The observed behaviour in the present study generally confirms the conclusions drawn from the velocity data. The adiabatic compressibility values are larger in L-glutamine compared to L-asparagine, L-lysine which shows molecular association/interaction is greater in L-glutamine than that of other two amino acids. Amino acid molecules

in neutral solution exist in the dipolar form and thus have stronger interaction with the surrounding water molecules. The increasing electrostrictive compression of water around the molecules results in a large decrease in the compressibility of solutions.

The interaction between the solute and water molecules in the solvent is termed as hydration. From the Table 2, it is observed that the values of n_H are positive in all systems studied and such positive values of n_H are found to increase with increasing the content of solutes, but it decreases with increasing the concentration of glycerine in all systems studied. The increasing values of n_H indicate the hydration effect. The decreasing behaviour of n_H shows that glycerine has a solute-co-solute interaction and vice-versa.

Table 2. Values of adiabatic compressibility (β), hydration number (n_H) of amino acids in aqueous glycerine solutions at 303.15 K

Molarity (M) (mol dm ⁻³)	β ($\times 10^{-10}$ m ² N ⁻¹)			n_H		
				Water + glycerine		
	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M
System-I : Water + glycerine + L-glutamine						
0.00	4.4074	4.2861	4.1806	-	-	-
0.02	4.3977	4.2144	4.1382	6.1	39.0	20.3
0.04	4.3769	4.1708	4.1171	9.6	31.4	15.3
0.06	4.3553	4.1205	4.0543	10.9	29.9	20.3
0.08	4.2902	4.0983	4.0029	18.5	25.6	21.4
0.10	4.1617	4.0706	3.9175	30.9	23.5	25.3
System-II : Water + glycerine + L-asparagine						
0.00	4.4074	4.2861	4.1806	-	-	-
0.02	4.3681	4.2045	4.0457	24.7	44.3	64.8
0.04	4.3466	4.1564	4.0038	19.2	35.3	48.6
0.06	4.2078	4.0986	3.9851	41.9	34.0	31.4
0.08	4.1302	4.0716	3.9649	43.7	29.2	25.9
0.10	4.0856	4.0346	3.9050	40.6	27.3	26.5
System-III : Water + glycerine + L-lysine						
0.00	4.4074	4.2861	4.1806	-	-	-
0.02	4.3793	4.2608	4.1342	17.7	13.8	22.3
0.04	4.3351	4.2310	4.0738	22.8	14.9	25.7
0.06	4.2906	4.1872	4.0595	24.5	17.9	19.4
0.08	4.2365	4.1762	4.0285	26.9	14.9	18.3
0.10	4.1643	4.0422	3.9218	30.6	26.6	24.9

Table 3. Values of apparent molal compressibility (ϕ_K) and apparent molal volume (ϕ_V) of amino acids in aqueous glycerine solutions at 303.15 K

Molarity (M) (mol dm ⁻³)	$-\phi_K$ ($\times 10^{-8}$ m ² N ⁻¹)			$-\phi_V$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹)		
				Water + glycerine		
	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M	0.0 M	0.5 M	1.0 M
System-I : Water + glycerine + L-glutamine						
0.02	8.9	38.2	23.4	94.1	53.9	52.8
0.04	11.0	31.6	18.5	77.1	63.7	62.3
0.06	11.8	30.2	23.7	71.4	61.9	62.2
0.08	17.9	26.1	25.2	73.6	59.8	69.3
0.10	27.8	24.2	29.3	71.7	61.5	70.6
System-II : Water + glycerine + L-asparagine						
0.02	25.6	44.7	71.5	109.2	83.4	95.9
0.04	19.8	35.7	48.1	104.7	75.9	91.0
0.06	38.5	34.3	36.0	119.1	70.1	79.7
0.08	39.6	29.9	30.3	110.8	70.8	76.4
0.10	36.8	28.1	30.9	103.5	68.3	78.2
System-III : Water + glycerine + L-lysine						
0.02	21.3	20.7	29.9	164.4	186.0	158.2
0.04	23.3	19.3	32.4	119.9	127.1	133.9
0.06	24.8	20.7	25.3	121.3	97.6	119.3
0.08	26.6	17.9	23.6	117.0	96.2	107.2
0.10	29.5	28.9	31.1	117.3	104.9	98.0

The following observations have been made on apparent molal compressibility ϕ_K and apparent molal volume ϕ_V (Table 3) of the three amino acids in aqueous glycerine mixtures at 303.15 K.

(i) The values of ϕ_K and ϕ_v are all negative over the entire range of molarity of amino acids and also an increase of glycerine content.

(ii) The negative ϕ_K values are decreasing with increasing the concentration of amino acids as well as glycerine contents.

(iii) The negative ϕ_v values are increasing with increasing the concentrations of amino acids as well as glycerine.

(iv) The magnitude of ϕ_v is in order : L-lysine < L-asparagine < L-glutamine.

All the observations clearly suggest that the negative values of ϕ_K and ϕ_v in all systems indicate the presence of ion-solvent interactions. Further, the negative values of ϕ_v indicate electrostrictive solvation of ions¹³. The observed increasing behaviour of ϕ_v suggest the existence of strong ion-solvent interaction in all system studied. The negative value of ϕ_K indicate ionic and hydrophilic interactions occurring in these systems. Since more number of water molecules are available at lower concentration of glycerine, the chances for the penetration of solute molecules into the solvent molecules is highly favoured. The observed behaviour of ϕ_K which reveals that the strengthening of ion-solvent interaction in all systems studied. Further, from the magnitude of ϕ_v , it can be concluded that strong molecular association is found in L-glutamine than the other two amino acids.

The limiting apparent molar compressibility ϕ_K^0 provides information regarding ion-solvent interactions and S_K , that of ion-ion interactions in the solution. From Table 4 it is observed that ϕ_K^0 values are negative and it decreases with increasing the concentration of glycerine in all systems studied. Appreciable negative values of ϕ_K^0 and its behaviour for all systems reinforce our earlier view of existence of ion-solvent interactions in the mixture. The values of S_K exhibits positive with increasing the concentration of glycerine in all the three amino acids but it is found to be negative without addition of glycerine content. This behaviour indicates the existence of ion-solute interaction with increase in glycerine content and suggests structure making/breaking effect of the amino acids. It is well known that solutes causing electrostriction lead to decrease in the compressibility of the solution. This is reflected by the negative values of ϕ_K of the amino acids.

The volume behaviour of a solute at infinite dilution is satisfactorily represented by ϕ_v^0 which is independent of the ion-ion interactions and provides information con-

cerning ion-solvent interactions. Table 4 reveals that the values of ϕ_v^0 are negative and it increases with the addition of glycerine contents in all systems studied. The increase in ϕ_v^0 may be attributed to the increased hydrophilicity/polar character of the side chain of the amino acids. The magnitude of ϕ_v^0 is in the order : L-glutamine > L-asparagine > L-lysine. It is evident from the Table 4 that S_v exhibits positive values in all systems, suggesting the presence of strong ion-ion interaction. Generally, the following types of interactions occurring between the amino acid molecules and glycerine molecules :

(i) Hydrophilic-ionic interactions between -OH group of glycerine and Zwitterionic centres of the amino acids.

(ii) Hydrophilic-hydrophilic interactions between the -OH group of glycerine and OH group of the amino acids.

(iii) Hydrophilic-hydrophobic interactions between the -OH group of glycerine and the non-polar side group of the amino acids.

(iv) Hydrophobic-hydrophobic interaction between the non-polar side groups of the glycerine and amino acids.

Similar types of interaction were also suggested by Lin *et al.*¹⁴ in their study of enthalpic behaviour of some amino acids in aqueous saccharides. The $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values (Table 4) can also be explained on the basis of co-sphere overlap model¹⁵ in terms of solute-co-solute interactions. According to this model the hydrophilic-ionic group interactions contribute positively, whereas hydrophobic-hydrophobic group interactions contribute negatively. Therefore from Fig. 1, the positive $\Delta\phi_v^0$ values observed for L-glutamine and L-asparagine suggest that former type of interactions are dominating over the latter.

Fig. 1. Variation of transfer volume of some α -amino acids with aqueous glycerine solutions at 303.15 K.

Table 4. Values of limiting apparent molar compressibility (ϕ_K^0), limiting apparent molar volume (ϕ_V^0) and their constants S_K and S_V , transfer volumes ($\Delta\phi_V^0$) and A and B coefficients of Jones-Dole equation of amino acids in aqueous glycerine solution at 303.15 K

Amino acids	Molarity (M)	ϕ_K^0 ($\times 10^{-8}$ m ² N ⁻¹)	ϕ_V^0 ($\times 10^{-3}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹)	S_K ($\times 10^{-8}$ N ⁻¹ m ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	S_V ($\times 10^{-3}$ m ³ l ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})	$\Delta\phi_V^0$ ($\times 10^{-3}$ m ³ mol ⁻¹)	A (dm ^{3/2} mol ^{-1/2})	B (dm ³ mol ⁻¹)
L-Glutamine	0	-0.57	-97.20	-68.50	83.65	-	-0.16	2.65
	0.5	-42.90	-55.05	54.87	21.84	42.15	-1.97	8.69
	1.0	-17.70	-46.97	26.90	70.38	50.23	-0.12	4.37
L-Asparagine	0	-16.27	-110.78	-67.52	5.65	-	-0.13	1.24
	0.5	-49.40	-87.61	63.80	59.49	23.17	-0.03	1.27
	1.0	-82.64	-103.61	167.86	82.79	7.17	-0.41	4.35
L-Lysine	0	-17.76	-168.19	-31.37	171.88	-	-0.43	1.74
	0.5	-16.73	-201.08	20.40	336.43	-32.89	-0.01	1.15
	1.0	-31.69	-179.68	14.65	240.70	-11.49	-0.16	4.29

From Table 4, it is observed that the values of A are negative and B coefficients are positive. Further the values of B are increased with increasing the content of glycerine in all the three amino acids. Since A is a measure of ionic interaction¹⁶, it is evident that there is an existence of ion-ion interaction in the amino acids studied, which is indicated by the smaller magnitude of A values. B -coefficient is also known as measure of order or disorder introduced by a solute in to the solvent. It is also a measure of ion-solvent interaction and it is directly dependent on the size, shape and charge of the solute molecules. Thus, B -values reflect the net structural effects of the solute and solvent molecules. The positive behaviour of B -coefficients in all the amino acids suggests the existence of strong ion-solvent interaction. The magnitude of B values in the order : L-glutamine > L-asparagine > L-lysine. This conclusion is in excellent agreement with that drawn from S_V and ϕ_V^0 data and the larger values of B indicate structure making capacity of the solute.

Conclusion :

In the present research, volumetric, compressibility and transport parameters of L-glutamine, L-asparagine and L-lysine in water and aqueous glycerine solution at 303.15 K were obtained using density, viscosity and ultrasonic velocity data and the results have been used to study the existence of ion-solvent interactions. From the magnitude of ϕ_V^0 and the values of B -coefficient it can be concluded that L-glutamine possesses strong ion-solvent interaction than the other two amino acids. The transfer volume $\Delta\phi_V^0$ data suggest that hydrophilic-ionic group interactions are dominating over the hydrophobic-hydrophobic group interactions.

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